

NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth Report

NFDI4Earth Community and Target Groups

NFDI4Earth Community Composition and Estimation of relevant Earth System Sciences and Research Data Management Target Groups

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Executive summary

This document provides estimates and characterisations regarding the makeup of the NFDI4Earth community and the prospective user base for the NFDI4Earth services. The estimates draw from a variety of different sources, including official statistics from the Federal Statistical Office of Germany, governmental agencies, scientific communities, high-performance computing providers, RDM support structures, and a survey conducted at selected conferences.

Abbreviations

DFG – Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation)

DKRZ – Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (German Climate Computing Center)

DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst (German Weather Service)

EGU – European Geosciences Union

ESS – Earth System Sciences

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

GCS – Gauss Centre for Supercomputing

HPC – High-Performance Computing

NFDI – Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (National Research Data Infrastructure)

NHR – Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen (National High-Performance Computing)

RDM – Research Data Management

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1. Introduction

NFDI4Earth is the consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany addressing the digital needs of ESS which comprise a sizeable number of disciplines and communities with the overarching aim to understand the functioning of all subsystems of the Earth system – i.e. Geo-, Bio-, Hydro-, Atmosphere and Anthroposphere and their interactions.

This document provides estimates and characterisations regarding the makeup of the NFDI4Earth community and the prospective user base for the NFDI4Earth services, such as the OneStop4All (<https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>). The estimates draw from a variety of different sources. With these descriptions of the community, and concrete sizes of groups and members, we aim to better understand the target groups in order to align the NFDI4Earth services to the community's needs.

According to its two proposals from October 2020 and August 2025, NFDI4Earth addresses the following **research areas of the DFG Review Boards**: Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research (3.41); Geology and Palaeontology (3.42); Geophysics and Geodesy (3.43); Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry (3.44), Geography (3.45); Water Research (3.46) as well as the DFG Subject Areas: Soil Sciences (2.31-01); Ecology of Land Use (2.31-04); Forestry (2.31-06); Urbanism, Spatial Planning, Transportation and Infrastructure Planning, Landscape Planning (4.51-02); Geotechnics, Hydraulic Engineering (4.51-06).

Using this context from the proposals as a starting point, we examined the proportions of Earth System Science (ESS) within several basic populations:

- individuals at different career levels in academia based on official statistics,
- the data contribution of governmental agencies related to ESS to the data collection of all agencies on the portal GovData,
- the range of scientific communities related to ESS within academia,
- the RDM support structures associated with the relevant domains, and
- the structure of high-performance computing centres providing computing power and also acting as contributors and stakeholders in NFDI4Earth.

Finally, we also carried out a survey at selected conferences and workshops to inquire about the background and requirements of potential users of the NFDI4Earth services.

While not comprehensive, these estimates offer a general overview of the community composition and potential rough number of people involved in ESS and its sub-disciplines, with a primary emphasis on the German ESS community.

Further details about our approach and each evaluated source of information are outlined in the following sections.

2. Federal Statistical Office of Germany

The Federal Statistical Office of Germany ([Statistisches Bundesamt](#)) holds information on staff and student numbers in German universities. This gives us a good overview of the distribution of students and staff in ESS across different career levels in academia. We queried the portal for the year 2023, in all disciplines related to Earth System Science, and in the following groups:

- [Full-time academic staff](#)
- [Students in winter semester 2023/2024](#)
- [PhD students](#)
- [Professors](#)

These statistics were collected to understand the scale and composition of the Earth System Science community within German universities, as students and staff form the core of ESS education and research, this insight ensures that the portal's resources can be tailored to their needs.

Since each group contained information across all subject areas in Germany, we only selected subjects that are related to Earth System Science for our assessment. The full list of selected subjects can be found in sec. A.1. These subjects go beyond the specific research areas defined in the proposals (see above), but the classification schemes do not match.

For the group 'Full time academic staff' subjects including mathematics and natural sciences, physical sciences, life sciences, geosciences and geography, environmental and land management, engineering fields, spatial planning, and computer science were selected.

For 'Students in winter semester 2023/2024', the selected subjects span a broad range of disciplines relevant to Earth System Science, including natural sciences, environmental and geosciences, agricultural and forestry sciences, engineering fields, spatial planning and surveying, computer science, renewable energy, and related interdisciplinary studies. See sec. A.1 for a full list.

The selected subject areas for PhD students encompass social sciences, education, and communication science, alongside core disciplines in mathematics and natural sciences, physical sciences, life sciences, geosciences and geography, agricultural and forestry sciences, environmental and land management, engineering fields, spatial planning and surveying, and computer science. See sec. A.1 for a full list.

For professors, the subject group "mathematics, natural science" was selected. The results of each query are shown in Fig. 1.

The diversity of subjects and topics related to ESS within Germany highlights the importance of focusing on a broad range of target users within NFDI4Earth. Also, the distribution of people across different career stages could influence how we design and cater to users of our education

Figure 1: Total numbers of staff and students in ESS fields at German universities from 2023

Figure 2: Relative proportions of ESS staff and students at German universities compared to numbers across all disciplines for 2023; the total across all subject areas includes ESS numbers.

and training portal. We also compared the numbers in each group in ESS to the total numbers across all disciplines at German Universities (see Fig. 2). Here we can see the significance of subjects related to ESS within German universities when compared to overall numbers of students and staff across all disciplines.

3. Governmental Agencies on Federal and State Level with ESS Relation

Governmental agencies are both data providers and users of the NFDI4Earth services, additional to, for example, the universities and other research institutions. In assessing the number of agencies that are related to ESS we want to gain a better understanding of the proportion and variety of the contribution of these agencies to NFDI4Earth.

There is no comprehensive official list of agencies on different levels (country, federal state, region, community) available. We therefore tried to roughly estimate a number of governmental agencies related to ESS via a query to the GovData portal which brings together data from all agencies at a federal level. The tag GDI-DE, which stands for the German Geodata Infrastructure, was used for the query, as a proxy for the ESS relation. With this query we can

then estimate a number of agencies with ESS relation that submitted data to GovData. This is only a rough estimate and by far not comprehensive, as not all agencies are connected to GovData yet.

The query (from 03/2025) yielded a list of 649 entities. This list covers all levels of administrative responsibility. We then filtered this list to remove the city- and community-level agencies. We were able to reduce the list so that only higher federal authorities, federal offices, state authorities, and other state-related institutions remained on the list. There was a total of 87 institutions that provided data. The list of agencies can be found in sec. A.2. However, the list is not comprehensive, and many agencies are missing because they did not submit data to GovData yet.

For comparison, we also searched Wikipedia for a list of governmental agencies on the highest (country) level which had relation to ESS. This search already yielded 41 agencies (see also sec. A.2), hinting at a lack of submitted data from ESS-related agencies to GovData.

Our estimate shows that the landscape of governmental agencies is quite diverse across different administrative levels. A lot of agencies are not well connected, neither to GovData nor to NFDI4Earth. Hence there are two tasks that could be important for a successful integration of the agencies in NFDI4Earth: 1) Support reusability of published governmental data by collecting and providing existing standards and by reporting existing good practices and workflows from agencies that successfully make their data available. 2) Facilitate discussion among the agencies by communicating the need for harmonised access to governmental data from the larger ESS community.

4. Scientific Communities (Fachgesellschaften)

A professional association or society is an organisation of people who are scientifically active or interested in a particular field. Similar terms commonly used in science are 'scientific professional associations' or 'academic societies'. This actually applies to all disciplines and is not specific to the Earth System Sciences and is used interchangeably in this work.

An academic society is usually an association of people working in science, or those who have achieved a certain level of qualification in a scientific field. These societies comprehend institutional as well as individual memberships. These types of associations can also be interdisciplinary and may themselves have further subdivisions, e. g., in form of academies.

In our case, the definition of a subject canon can be based in general on all subsystems of the Earth System – i.e. Geo-, Bio-, Hydro-, Atmosphere and Anthroposphere, and to a limited extent on the DFG review boards from the NFDI4Earth proposals (see introduction). Instead, the fields and subjects should be based on all relevant Earth system compartments, i.e., all relevant

Earth system compartments should be addressed, such as **atmosphere** (climate, meteorology), **hydrosphere** (ocean and inland waters), **geosphere** (solid Earth and soil sciences), and to a certain extent also **cryosphere**, **biosphere**, and **anthroposphere**.

The professional associations in these thematic fields are an important part of the scientific system and its development, but unlike in other consortia, especially from the humanities (such as NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Objects, ...) or the so-called specialised information services (such as FID GEO), they have only played a minor role in NFDI4Earth to date.

However, they can play a significant role, particularly as multipliers in their respective communities, and should be used for a stronger community engagement, as channels for the dissemination process of the NFDI4Earth products and services, and as a target group themselves for transformation and cultural change around RDM. Academic societies often maintain communication structures and reach sub-communities across all career levels, for example through interest groups or regular events. In this context, an advantage of integrating academic societies in the NFDI4Earth network could also be their specific organisations for junior researchers, i.e., access to various career levels and by sub-divisions for Early Career Scientists, such as the Junge DMG or Junge DGGV.

An **AI search** looking for '**Fachgesellschaften**' (membership organisations with scientific goal/s), '**Arbeitskreise**' (within or outside the membership organisations), '**Interessensgruppen**' (loose networks), '**Konsortien & Verbände**' (institutional cooperations, often based on a limited funding), '**Cluster & Plattformen**' (mostly research strategic) in Earth System Sciences gave a first estimate of over 60 organisations, yielding decent results. From our point of view, there are potentially more groups as well as associations that were not covered by the query. Some items were added manually to the list.

The search prompt was specified with the ESS subdisciplines with a focus on Earth System compartments. Of those approximately more than 60 results, about one quarter are actually 'Fachgesellschaften'. The number of members organised in these associations cannot exactly be estimated because this information is not publicly available, but an approximate target group size can be estimated based on the size of the professional associations linked with an individual Earth system compartment. We use the 'Hydrosphere' as a reference compartment since there was a study published in 2012, "Wasserforschung in Deutschland", where the authors tried to estimate the relevant institutions of water research (UFZ, 2012 – estimation see the following section). An update of a list of relevant associations embedded in according communities and based on the query mentioned above can be found in sec. A.3.

An estimate of the target group size was based on using a pre-selection of professional associations linked to the main Earth system compartments (Atmosphere, Hydrosphere, Geosphere, Biosphere and Anthroposphere) and its corresponding disciplines and calculated as follows:

The Hydrosociences was used as the reference discipline and Water research as reference sub-domain community, for which an estimate of relevant research sites (150) and working groups (450) was made in 2012 (UFZ); assuming an average working group size of about 20 people, this results in a total of approximately 9.000 scientists and employees of the Hydrosociences community which is represented by in total nine academic societies. It was further assumed that the Geosciences community is approximately one third larger (in total 15 academic societies), while the Biosciences and the Atmospheric Sciences are only represented by three and one academic societies – analogous to the Anthroposphere and interdisciplinary ESS Sciences which accounts for the smallest share. All affiliated professional associations are listed in sec. A.3. This leads to a calculation of approximately 32.900 people in total potentially working in the field of ESS. Finally, if we assume that both research sites and working groups overlap — i.e., that they are often interdisciplinary (working) groups, the number is significantly reduced. Assuming a 33% overlap, this leaves approximately 21,700 scientists.

The number of abstracts submitted to the General Assembly of the European Geoscience Union (EGU) for 2024 and 2025 was used as a control variable for this assessment, where the disciplines were assigned based on the EGU's designated (but assorted) programme groups.

With a total sum of approximately 20,000 abstracts, this results in the following approximate distribution: 21% Atmospheric Sciences, 8% Bio(geo)sciences, 3% Cryospheric Sciences, 25% Geosciences, 19% Hydrosociences and 23% interdisciplinary Sciences (or cannot be clearly assigned). The calculation is again based on the same assumption as for the professional associations – i. e., using water research as the reference value, but results in a larger target community due to the non-assignable disciplines (with a share of 23%) of approximately 46.700 people. After deducting the 33% overlap between disciplines and working groups outlined above, this results in a target figure of approximately 31.000 scientists.

However, with regard to methodology, it should be critically noted that the EGU is an international conference – and therefore the number of scientists potentially working in the field of ESS is higher and only of limited relevance to the national ESS community or scene, but can certainly serve as a guide or benchmark.

As mentioned above, academic societies offer direct access to the ESS community and its sub-communities. This access enables both a quantitative estimate of the target group and access to specific target groups for marketing or disseminating NFDI4Earth services. These societies usually hold regular annual conferences and organise community events where NFDI4Earth and its outputs can be promoted.

Experiences from, for example, the FID GEO and others shows that there is still room for improvement in terms of Earth system-related research data management – i.e., subject-specific formats (as sessions, workshops, lectures and others) can be implemented to promote NFDI4Earth's or also partner services. It is vital that such formats are repeated or established

as event series to step-by-step create a sustainable culture of RDM in ESS.

Finally, individual contact points within the most relevant scientific societies could be identified to integrate them in NFDI4Earth for targeted networking. These contacts may complement contacts to the current 67 NFDI4Earth partnering institutions.

5. Providers for High Performance Computing in Germany

High-performance computing (HPC) is a key pillar of Earth and environmental sciences, as many scientific questions—for example, in climate and weather modelling, geophysics, hydrology, or remote sensing—are characterised by data-intensive and computationally demanding processes. HPC providers supply the essential infrastructure for this, while HPC users develop and operate specialised modelling, simulation, and data processing workflows. NFDI4Earth is aimed at both groups because interoperable data spaces, standardised pipelines, reusable workflows, and FAIR-compliant data management are fundamental prerequisites for sustainable and reproducible research in HPC environments.

The HPC institutions listed (see sec. A.4) form the backbone of Germany's national research landscape in scientific computing. They represent three complementary groups: the **GCS (Gauss Centre for Supercomputing)** as the Tier-1 national centres, the **NHR (National High-Performance Computing) centres** as the university-based Tier-2 infrastructures, and the broader network of **Gauss Alliance institutions**, which includes specialised research organisations with domain-specific mandates. Together, they cover a wide spectrum of scientific needs without requiring researchers to engage deeply with technical complexities.

The three GCS centres—JSC, HLRS, and LRZ—provide the country's most powerful computational resources and enable large-scale scientific projects that rely on complex models and extensive datasets. Their role is to support research that demands national-level capacity, including significant shares of climate, environmental, and geoscientific modelling. The NHR centres complement this capability by offering broad access for researchers at universities across Germany. They combine computational resources with scientific support and advisory services, and several of them—such as NHR@KIT, NHR-Nord, and NHR@ZIB—maintain explicit focus areas related to Earth System Sciences, including atmospheric dynamics, ocean modelling, or geodata analysis.

The Gauss Alliance adds a third essential pillar to this ecosystem. It brings together institutions whose HPC environments are tailored to highly specialised scientific communities. Among them, the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) stands out as the national service platform for climate research, supporting simulations that underpin major climate assessments and long-term projections. The German Weather Service (DWD) forms another crucial component with its operational atmospheric models, while the Alfred Wegener Institute and

the GeoForschungsZentrum provide dedicated computing for polar, ocean, and solid Earth research. These institutions rely on domain-specific workflows and data infrastructures that are tightly aligned with the needs of their respective subdisciplines. All four institutions are members of NFDI4Earth.

Taken together, the GCS centres, NHR infrastructures, and Gauss Alliance institutions create a well-coordinated national HPC ecosystem. Researchers can access the most suitable environment for their scientific questions—whether they involve large-scale Earth system simulations, university-based methodological development, or specialised modelling in atmospheric, oceanic, or geophysical sciences. This integrated structure ensures that Germany remains internationally competitive in scientific computing while enabling users to focus on their research rather than on technical system details.

Precise user numbers for these HPC institutions are not publicly available. This is because most centres report their activity in terms of projects and scientific domains rather than individual users, and many operate within collaborative research structures where teams—rather than single researchers—access the systems. Additionally, some organisations, especially within the Gauss Alliance, serve mixed internal and external communities, making a unified, transparent count difficult to maintain or meaningfully compare across centres.

HPC providers and users make a significant contribution to the further development of NFDI4Earth: they provide practical requirements for scalable data and workflow services, support the integration of computing and data infrastructures, and contribute valuable expertise in performance, optimisation, and technical standards. In addition, they act as drivers of innovative data processing technologies and, through their feedback, enable the continuous improvement of NFDI4Earth services for the entire Earth system community.

6. RDM Support Structures in Germany

RDM (Research Data Management) support centres are indispensable partners for sustainable and quality-assured research data management in the Earth and environmental sciences. They advise researchers on FAIR principles, metadata standards, data publication, repositories, workflows, and long-term archiving, thereby directly supporting the implementation of NFDI goals. RDM support staff, such as data stewards, are one of the key target groups for NFDI4Earth, as they bring the developed services, standards, and best practices to local research and infrastructure landscapes and anchor them there.

Support for RDM in Germany has become highly professionalised in recent years and is now well developed, though still unevenly distributed. At the national level, the **National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)** forms the central backbone: it consists of more than two dozen discipline-specific consortia that develop tailored services, standards, tools, and advisory

offerings for nearly all scientific fields. These are complemented by cross-cutting initiatives (e.g., Base4NFDI) as well as specialised competence centres, such as GESIS for the social sciences.

In parallel, most German universities and research organisations have established their own RDM service units, typically located in university libraries, IT service centres, or research support offices. These units commonly provide consulting, training, support with data management plans, guidance on repository selection, and technical solutions for data storage and publication. The coverage, however, is not uniform: larger universities often maintain professional teams and well-established workflows, while smaller institutions may only offer basic support or decentralised contact persons.

6.1. How much RDM support is there in Germany? (Estimation)

There is no precise official number, but based on the current landscape we can make a well-grounded estimate:

- NFDI consortia / national actors: approximately 25–30 large structural programs, each involving numerous institutions.
- Universities / higher education institutions: Germany has around 120 universities, of which at least 70–80 demonstrably have a dedicated RDM service unit or centralised support. Many others have designated contacts within libraries, IT centres, or faculties.
- Research organisations (Fraunhofer, Leibniz, Helmholtz, Max Planck): nearly all major institutes have established RDM structures or participate in NFDI initiatives.

Realistically, Germany hosts more than 150 institutional RDM support units (and growing), supplemented by several major national programs. As a result, RDM support is broadly available across the German research landscape — even though the depth and maturity of services still vary by institution.

A comprehensive [list](#) of research data management service units, networking organisations, research data centres, data competence centres, and NFDI initiatives has been compiled on *Forschungsdaten.info*. Further investigation into the connection with the ESS community and its institutions is planned for the continuation phase of NFDI4Earth.

RDM support units make a significant contribution to NFDI4Earth by providing institutional expertise, established materials, and training offers. Their experience and existing support structures enable effective dissemination and adoption of NFDI4Earth concepts. At the same time, they act as important nodes for networking and communication: they connect local communities, infrastructure providers, and NFDI initiatives, thereby promoting the exchange and shared use of tools, services, and best practices.

Therefore, there is a mutual benefit, and the collaboration is reciprocal:

- NFDI4Earth benefits from the deep expertise of RDM support units as well as from their materials, training formats, and proven advisory processes. These resources feed into the continuous improvement, scalability, and relevance of NFDI4Earth services.
- RDM support units benefit from the technical solutions, training opportunities, standards, and community-driven offerings provided by NFDI4Earth. This enables them to broaden and modernise their own support portfolio and align it more closely with the needs of Earth and environmental science communities.

7. Survey on Target Group

Measure 2.1 and also at the dedicated OneStop4All feedback workshops at DKRZ and KIT. The survey consisted of four questions:

- What is your primary field of work?
- How relevant would a central platform with data, services and tools etc. as well as learning materials for Earth System Science be for your work?
- What is your typical role in research projects?
- Which topics are you most interested in?

As of mid of June 2026, we received altogether 60 submissions to the survey. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

These respondents can only hint at the overall structure of the community and cannot be seen as a representative sample.

The results from the question 'What is your primary field of work', are quite distributed, however we see a larger proportion in the fields of Atmospheric science, geosciences and Climate research. These results were expected as the majority of survey participants were from the EGU General Assembly meeting which has a strong focus on these fields of work.

The results from this question (Fig. 4) show that the vast majority of participants would find such a platform either very relevant or at least interesting for their prospective work.

The results from this question (Fig. 5) show that the majority of participants are either researchers or scientists or students or PhD candidates. This finding could influence the focus and content of the OneStop4All portal as it tells us which career level the majority of potential users that took the survey are at.

The results from the final question (Fig. 6) show a varied distribution, however a majority of participants are interested in getting access to data. This is closely followed by data analysis

Figure 3: Results from the survey question "What is your primary field of work?"

Figure 4: Results from the question “How relevant would a central platform with data, services and tools etc., as well as learning materials for Earth System Science be for your work?”

Figure 5: Results from the survey question “What is your typical role in research projects?”

Figure 6: Results from the survey question “What topics are you most interested in?”

tools and data visualisation. These results show that a primary focus of our target group could be accessing and working with data.

Overall, the results from the survey can be interpreted that the Earth System Science community faces challenges that can be answered by a centralised portal like the OneStop4All. Topics related to data, such as data access, data analysis, and data visualisation, emerged as the most relevant areas, suggesting these should be a key focus for the portal’s future development. Notably, the majority of survey participants were researchers or students, highlighting the importance of tailoring resources to support both academic and research needs.

8. Implications and Conclusions

The overview of community composition and target groups reveals, that NFDI4Earth operates within a highly diverse landscape of institutions, subject areas or disciplines, career stages, and technical backgrounds. This diversity has implications for the design, communication, and long-term sustainability of NFDI4Earth services. Despite the heterogeneity of the assessed groups, several general conclusions can be drawn, accompanied by more specific implications for key user communities. These implications and conclusions are as follows.

Across all analysed domains, it becomes clear that ESS research in Germany is **broad and fragmented**. Researchers and students span a large number of subject areas, ranging from classical geosciences to engineering, environmental sciences, computer science, and interdisciplinary fields. This implies, that NFDI4Earth must offer services that speak to very

different levels of expertise, workflows, culture, and expectations concerning the management of research data. Entry-level users require accessible guidance, structured training materials, and intuitive navigation, while experienced researchers expect efficient access to data, tools, and workflows that integrate seamlessly into complex research environments. Technically versed fields may have higher standards towards computational reproducibility, fields typically working with public data may have a higher degree of sharing or openness and discovery of resources using public catalogues, while small sub-areas may be more familiar with personal recommendations or networking to meet their needs.

The analysis of governmental agencies highlights another structural challenge: many ESS-related institutions contribute substantial data, yet the degree of **connectivity and standardisation on public data publications remains uneven**. For NFDI4Earth, this suggests a dual role—on the one hand, supporting agencies in improving reusability through standards, documentation and best practices, and on the other hand, facilitating dialogue across institutional boundaries. A stronger exchange between agencies and the ESS research community is essential to foster harmonised access to crucial environmental data. The NFDI4Earth services can act as a mediating space that makes existing practices more transparent and demonstrates the broader scientific value of standardised data provision.

Scientific associations represent an underestimated target group. They serve as multipliers, maintain established communication channels, and reach sub-communities across all career levels, including early-career researchers. Involving associations can significantly enhance outreach, improve dissemination of NFDI4Earth services, and provide opportunities for continuous feedback from domain communities. Integrating NFDI4Earth more systematically into regular events and communication structures of associations would support long-term community engagement and help develop subject-specific formats for research data management within the NFDI4Earth services.

High-performance computing providers are a target group forming another essential pillar of the ecosystem. These providers operate at the intersection of scientific modelling, workflow development, and data-intensive research. Because many HPC users also design tools, maintain pipelines, or teach methods, they can naturally act as validators and ambassadors for NFDI4Earth services. Their input is crucial for ensuring interoperability, scalability, and performance. At the same time, HPC centres can contribute to co-design processes that align data infrastructures with computational needs, enhancing the scientific relevance of NFDI4Earth's solutions.

RDM support structures—both institutional and national—play a similarly important role. They provide established consulting formats, training materials, and long-standing experience with implementing FAIR principles and data governance. Close cooperation with these units strengthens standardisation, quality assurance, and dissemination of NFDI4Earth services. Moreover, RDM units serve as connectors between local communities, infrastructure

providers, and the broader NFDI network, enabling effective integration of NFDI4Earth services into institutional workflows.

The **survey** conducted at EGU and other events confirms several of these findings. The majority of respondents point to a central platform being useful for their work, and their interests clearly prioritise access to data, data analysis tools, and visualisation. Most participants are researchers, PhD candidates, or students, which aligns with the demographic patterns observed in the academic statistics. These results underscore the need to focus portal development on data-centric services, while ensuring that guidance and learning materials remain accessible to early-career users. Repeating such surveys periodically and broadening their dissemination would allow NFDI4Earth to monitor evolving community needs and evaluate the effectiveness of its service portfolio.

Taken together, the findings illustrate both the opportunities and the complexity of addressing such a heterogeneous target landscape. NFDI4Earth must balance usability, technical depth, and flexibility while engaging with diverse stakeholders who differ not only in their disciplinary backgrounds but also in their institutional roles and infrastructural environments. The overarching implications are clear: NFDI4Earth should **continue** to prioritise interoperable and reusable data services; strengthen collaboration with multipliers such as scientific societies, RDM units, and HPC providers; and foster connections with governmental agencies to improve data accessibility. At the same time, it must maintain a user-centred approach that acknowledges the needs of different career levels and supports the community through training, intuitive interfaces, and well-documented tools.

Ultimately, the breadth of the assessed communities demonstrates that NFDI4Earth is positioned not merely as a technical provider but as a unifying actor within Earth System Science in Germany. Its success will depend on how effectively it can connect these communities, reduce fragmentation, and enable a coherent, sustainable research data landscape that reflects the needs of both current and future generations of ESS researchers.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Results from the Federal Statistical Office of Germany

The exact subject areas selected for the statistics from The Federal Statistical Office of Germany ([Statistisches Bundesamt](#)) are listed here:

For the group **'Full time academic staff'**:

- Mathematics, Natural Sciences, general
- Physics, Astronomy
- Chemistry
- Biology
- Geosciences (excluding Geography)
- Geography
- Agricult., Forest and Nutritional Sciences, gen.
- Land Management Engineering, Environmental Design
- Agricult. Sciences, Food and Beverage Technology
- Forest Science, Wood Science
- Engineering Sciences, general
- Mining, Metallurgy
- Spatial Planning
- Civil Engineering
- Surveying
- Computer Science

For **'Students in winter semester 2023/2024'**:

- Administrative Science/Public Administration
- Aeronautical and Aerospace Engineering
- Agricultural Biology
- Agricultural Economics
- Agricultural Science/Agriculture
- Applied Systems Science
- Area of study: Natural Sciences/General Studies
- Astrophysics and Astronomy

- Biochemistry
- Bioinformatics
- Biology
- Cartography
- Chemical Engineering/Chemical Process Technology
- Chemistry
- Civil Engineering/Structural Engineering
- Computer Science
- Economic/Social Geography
- Environmental Protection
- Environmental Technology (including Recycling)
- Forest Science, Forestry
- Geoecology
- Geography
- Geology/Palaeontology
- Geophysics
- Geosciences general
- Horticulture
- Hydraulic Engineering
- Interdisc. Studies (special. in Natural Sciences)
- Land Management Engineering/Landscape Design
- Landscape Ecology/Biogeography (ex. SF385 s. 2012)
- Meteorology
- Mine Surveying
- Mineralogy
- Mining/Mine Engineering
- Nature Conservation
- Nautical Science/Maritime Studies
- Oceanography
- Plant Production
- Renewable Energy
- Social Sciences
- Spatial Planning
- Surveying (Geodesy)
- Viticulture and Oenology
- Water Management

For PhD students:

- Social Sciences/Sociology

- Educational Sciences
- Communication Science/Journalism
- Mathematics, Natural Sciences
- Mathematics, Natural Sciences, general
- Physics, Astronomy
- Chemistry
- Biology
- Geosciences (excluding Geography)
- Geography
- Agricultural, Forest a.Nutr. Sciences, Veterin.Med.
- Land Management Engineering, Environmental Design
- Forest Science, Wood Science
- Engineering Sciences
- Engineering, general
- Mining, Metallurgy
- Traffic Engineering, Nautical Science
- Spatial Planning
- Civil Engineering
- Surveying
- Computer Science

For professors:

- Mathematics, Natural Sciences

A.2. List of governmental agencies related to ESS

Query on GovData with the tag GDI-DE; filtered list:

- Abteilung 4 LfU Gewässer
- Bayerische Landesanstalt für Wald und Forstwirtschaft (LWF)
- Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt
- Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Forsten
- Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Wirtschaft, Landesentwicklung und Energie
- Behörde für Umwelt, Klima, Energie und Agrarwirtschaft (BUKEA)
- Berliner Forsten
- Biosphärenreservatsverwaltung Niedersächsische Elbtalaue
- Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG)

- Bundesamt für Naturschutz
- Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie (BSH)
- Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe
- Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR)
- Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde, Federal Institute of Hydrology
- Deutscher Wetterdienst
- FGeoWSV - Fachstelle für Geodäsie und Geoinformatik der Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes
- Fischereiamt Berlin
- Freie Hansestadt Bremen, Die Senatorin für Umwelt, Klima und Wissenschaft
- GDWS - Generaldirektion Wasserstraßen und Schifffahrt
- Gemeinsame Landesplanungsabteilung Berlin-Brandenburg (GL)
- Gemeinsame Landesplanungsabteilung Berlin-Brandenburg, Referat GL 3
- Geobasis NRW
- Geologischer Dienst NRW
- Hessisches Landesamt für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation
- Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geologie (LBEG)
- Landesamt für Bergbau, Geologie und Rohstoffe Brandenburg (LBGR)
- Landesamt für Geobasisinformation Sachsen (GeoSN)
- Landesamt für Geoinformation und Landesvermessung Niedersachsen (LGLN)
- Landesamt für innere Verwaltung M-V, Amt für Geoinformation, Vermessung und Katasterwesen
- Landesamt für innere Verwaltung M-V, Amt für Geoinformation, Vermessungs- und Katasterwesen
- Landesamt für Ländliche Entwicklung, Landwirtschaft und Flurneuordnung (LELF)
- Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Klima Nordrhein-Westfalen - Nationalparkverwaltung Eifel
- Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Klima Nordrhein-Westfalen - Nationalparkverwaltung Eifel
- Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz Nordrhein-Westfalen

- Landesamt für Umwelt Brandenburg (LfU)
- Landesamt für Umwelt des Landes Schleswig-Holstein (LfU)
- Landesamt für Umwelt- und Arbeitsschutz
- Landesamt für Umweltschutz (LAU) Sachsen-Anhalt
- Landesamt für Vermessung und Geobasisinformation Rheinland-Pfalz
- Landesamt für Vermessung und Geoinformation (LVerGeo) Sachsen-Anhalt
- Landesamt für Vermessung und Geoinformation Schleswig-Holstein
- Landesamt für Vermessung, Geoinformation und Landentwicklung
- Landesamt GeoInformation Bremen
- Landesbetrieb Forst Brandenburg (LFB)
- Landesbetrieb für Küstenschutz, Nationalpark und Meeresschutz Schleswig-Holstein
- Landesbetrieb Geoinformation und Vermessung (LGV) Hamburg
- Landesbetrieb Straßen, Brücken und Gewässer
- Landesbetrieb Wald und Holz Nordrhein-Westfalen
- Landestalsperrenverwaltung Sachsen
- Landesvermessung und Geobasisinformation Brandenburg (LGB)
- Landwirtschaftskammer NRW
- Leibniz-Institut für Ökologische Raumentwicklung
- LUBW Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Württemberg
- Ministerium für Energiewende, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Natur (MEKUN)
- Ministerium für Energiewende, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Natur des Landes Schleswig-Holstein
- Ministerium für Energiewende, Klimaschutz, Umwelt und Natur des Landes Schleswig-Holstein
- Ministerium für Heimat, Kommunales, Bau und Digitalisierung des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen
- Ministerium für Land- und Ernährungswirtschaft, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz (MLEUV)
- Ministerium für Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz des Landes NRW
- Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLEV)

- Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, ländliche Räume, Europa und Verbraucherschutz (MLLEV)
- Ministerium für Umwelt, Klima, Mobilität, Agrar und Verbraucherschutz
- Ministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Verkehr des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen
- Ministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Verkehr des Landes NRW
- Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Industrie, Klimaschutz und Energie des Landes NRW
- Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Tourismus, Landwirtschaft und Forsten (MWL) Sachsen-Anhalt
- Nationalpark Harz
- Nationalparkverwaltung Niedersächsisches Wattenmeer
- Nationalparkverwaltung Niedersächsisches Wattenmeer / Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft Küsten- und Naturschutz
- Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz
- Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft, Küsten- und Naturschutz (NLWKN)
- Niedersächsisches Kompetenzzentrum Klimawandel
- Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Umwelt, Energie und Klimaschutz
- Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie
- Sächsisches Staatsministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit, Energie und Klimaschutz
- Senatsverwaltung für Mobilität, Verkehr, Klimaschutz und Umwelt Berlin
- Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung und Umwelt Berlin
- Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung, Bauen und Wohnen Berlin
- Senatsverwaltung für Umwelt, Mobilität, Verbraucher- und Klimaschutz, Fischereiamt Berlin
- Senatsverwaltung für Umwelt, Mobilität, Verbraucher- und Klimaschutz, Fischereiamt Berlin
- ThüringenForst AÖR, Forstliches Forschungs- und Kompetenzzentrum
- Thüringer Landesamt für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation
- Thüringer Landesamt für Landwirtschaft und Ländlichen Raum
- Thüringer Landesamt für Umwelt, Bergbau und Naturschutz
- Thüringer Landesverwaltungsamt
- Thüringer Ministerium für Infrastruktur und Landwirtschaft

- Umweltbundesamt

Search of agencies on the highest administrative levels:

1. Oberste Bundesbehörden:

- Bundesministerium für Landwirtschaft, Ernährung und Heimat
- Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Klimaschutz, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit

2. Bundesoberbehörden:

- Bundesamt für Infrastruktur, Umweltschutz und Dienstleistungen der Bundeswehr
- Bundesamt für Bauwesen und Raumordnung
- Bundesamt für Naturschutz
- Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie
- Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie
- Umweltbundesamt
- Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau
- Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde
- Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe
- Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut – Bundesforschungsinstitut für Ländliche Räume, Wald und Fischerei

3. Bundesmittel- und Bundesunterbehörden:

- Generaldirektion Wasserstraßen und Schifffahrt
- 8 Wasserstraßen-Neubauämter
- 17 Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsämter
- Reedereizentrum der Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung

4. Bundesanstalten:

- Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung
- Deutscher Wetterdienst (teilrechtsfähig)

A.3. List of academic societies related to ESS disciplinary sciences

Anthropospheric Sciences

- Gesellschaft für Nachhaltigkeit (GfN)

Atmospheric Sciences

- Deutsche Meteorologische Gesellschaft (DMG)

Bio(geo)sciences

- Gesellschaft für Ökologie (GfÖ)
- Geoökologische Gesellschaft (GÖG)
- Gesellschaft für Pflanzenökologie und Standortskunde

Cryospheric Sciences

- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Polarforschung (DGP)

Geosciences

- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Photogrammetrie
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Geodäsie (DVW)
- Geochemical Society - Deutsche Sektion (über DGGV)
- Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft (DBG)
- Deutsche Geologische Gesellschaft - Geologische Vereinigung (DGGV)
- Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft (DGG)
- Paläontologische Gesellschaft (PalGes)
- Arbeitskreis Quartärforschung (DEUQUA)
- Deutsche Mineralogische Gesellschaft (DMG)
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Kristallographie (DGK)
- Deutsche Geodätische Kommission (DGK)
- DEUQUA - Deutsche Quartärvereinigung
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Luft- und Raumfahrt - Fachbereich Planetenforschung
- Bundesverband Geothermie e. V.

Hydrosciences

- Deutsche Hydrologische Gesellschaft (DHG)
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Limnologie (DGL)
- Deutsche Gesellschaft für Meeresforschung (DGM)
- Deutsche Vereinigung für Wasserwirtschaft (DWA)
- Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfaches (DVGW)
- Bund der Ingenieure für Wasserwirtschaft (BWK)
- German Water Partnership
- Wasserchemische Gesellschaft
- Water Science Alliance e. V.

Interdisciplinary ESS Sciences

- Deutsches Komitee Katastrophenvorsorge (DKKV)

A.4. List of HPC centres in Germany

Table 1: HPC centres in Germany and their relation to Earth System Sciences

Category (Tier)	Centre / Institution	Example Systems	ESS Relation	Subdisciplines (if yes)
Tier 1 (GCS)	JSC – Forschungszentrum Jülich	JUPITER, JUWELS, JURECA-DC	Yes	Climate modelling, atmospheric physics, aerosols, ocean modelling, sea ice
Tier 1 (GCS)	HLRS – Stuttgart	Hawk, Hunter/Herder	Yes	Environmental modelling, climate projections, urban air quality, energy systems
Tier 1 (GCS)	LRZ – Garching	SuperMUC-NG, Blue Lion (planned)	Yes	Regional climate and atmospheric models, geophysics, hydrology
Tier 2 (NHR)	IT Center RWTH Aachen	CLAIX cluster	Partial	Fluid mechanics, atmospheric models (project-dependent)
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR@ZIB Berlin	Curta cluster	Yes	Earth system sciences, geodesy, fluid mechanics
Tier 2 (NHR)	ZIH – TU Dresden	HPC cluster	Partial	Climate/geodata analysis, geophysics
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR4Eng – TU Darmstadt	Lichtenberg II	Partial	Fluid dynamics, potentially atmosphere-related flows
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR@FAU Erlangen	HPC cluster	Partial	Geosciences, environmental modelling
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR-Nord – GWDG Göttingen	HPC cluster	Yes	Earth system sciences (general), fluid mechanics
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR@KIT – SCC Karlsruhe	HPC cluster	Yes	Atmosphere, ocean, climate dynamics, atmospheric chemistry
Tier 2 (NHR)	PC ² – Uni Paderborn	HPC cluster	No	
Tier 2 (NHR)	NHR Süd-West (Frankfurt/ Mainz/ Kaiserslautern/ Saarbrücken)	HPC cluster	Partial	Geosciences, numerical modelling
Special (ESS)	DKRZ – Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum	Levante	Yes	Climate modelling, atmospheric physics, oceanography, cryosphere, land surfaces
Special (ESS)	DWD – Deutscher Wetterdienst	Operational weather/climate computers	Yes	Numerical weather prediction, atmospheric dynamics, reanalysis
Special (ESS)	AWI – Alfred-Wegener-Institut	HPC cluster	Yes	Polar climate, sea ice, ocean modelling, biogeochemistry
Special (ESS)	GFZ – Deutsches GeoForschungsZentrum	HPC cluster	Yes	Seismology, geodynamics, geomagnetism, hydrology
Special	MPCDF – Max Planck Computing and Data Facility	HPC cluster	Partial	Atmosphere, ocean, biogeochemistry (depending on Max Planck Institute)
Special	DESY	HPC cluster	No	